

* Encoding: UTF-8.

DATASET ACTIVATE DataSet1.

UNIANOVA dev_azi_deg BY Reproduction Position

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/INTERCEPT=INCLUDE

/POSTHOC=Reproduction Position(BONFERRONI)

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/EMMEANS=TABLES(Position)

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/EMMEANS=TABLES(Reproduction*Position) COMPARE(Reproduction) ADJ(BONFERRONI)

/EMMEANS=TABLES(Reproduction*Position) COMPARE(Position) ADJ(BONFERRONI)

/PRINT DESCRIPTIVE

/CRITERIA=ALPHA(.05)

/DESIGN=Reproduction Position Reproduction*Position.

Univariate Analysis of Variance

Notes

Output Created		14-JUL-2024 16:21:14
Comments		
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Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics are based on all cases with valid data for all variables in the model.

Notes

Syntax	<pre> UNIANOVA dev_azi_deg BY Reproduction Position /METHOD=SSTYPE(3) /INTERCEPT=INCLUDE /POSTHOC=Reproduction Position(BONFERRONI) /PLOT=PROFILE (Position*Reproduction) TYPE=LINE ERRORBAR=NO MEANREFERENCE=NO YAXIS=AUTO /EMMEANS=TABLES (Reproduction) /EMMEANS=TABLES (Position) /EMMEANS=TABLES (Reproduction*Position) /EMMEANS=TABLES (Reproduction*Position) COMPARE(Reproduction) ADJ(BONFERRONI) /EMMEANS=TABLES (Reproduction*Position) COMPARE(Position) ADJ (BONFERRONI) /PRINT DESCRIPTIVE /CRITERIA=ALPHA(.05) /DESIGN=Reproduction Position Reproduction*Position. </pre>				
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Processor Time	00:00:03,95				
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Warnings

Post hoc tests are not performed for Reproduction because there are fewer than three groups.

Between-Subjects Factors

		N
Reproduction	CTC	324
	VBAP	333
Position	1	168
	2	171
	3	161
	4	157

Descriptive Statistics

Dependent Variable: dev_azi_deg

Reproduction	Position	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
CTC	1	-5.43585922	6.141222482	83
	2	-.539267712	8.966134365	85
	3	-3.33150253	16.25590609	79
	4	5.514157615	9.586593045	77
	Total	-1.03584146	11.50980585	324
VBAP	1	-4.27032067	6.469758870	85
	2	-5.43056686	11.87866297	86
	3	1.252574390	13.24220891	82
	4	5.997266057	10.17992398	80
	Total	-.743284151	11.61749499	333
Total	1	-4.84615221	6.317782099	168
	2	-2.99921933	10.78380210	171
	3	-.996755280	14.92925059	161
	4	5.760327522	9.864662690	157
	Total	-.887558991	11.55662486	657

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: dev_azi_deg

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	12270.051 ^a	7	1752.864	15.099	.000
Intercept	399.623	1	399.623	3.442	.064
Reproduction	18.447	1	18.447	.159	.690
Position	10323.693	3	3441.231	29.643	.000
Reproduction * Position	1923.075	3	641.025	5.522	.001
Error	75342.408	649	116.090		
Total	88130.018	657			
Corrected Total	87612.459	656			

a. R Squared = .140 (Adjusted R Squared = .131)

Estimated Marginal Means

1. Reproduction

Dependent Variable: dev_azi_deg

Reproduction	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
CTC	-.948	.599	-2.124	.228
VBAP	-.613	.591	-1.773	.547

2. Position

Dependent Variable: dev_azi_deg

Position	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	-4.853	.831	-6.486	-3.221
2	-2.985	.824	-4.603	-1.367
3	-1.039	.849	-2.707	.628
4	5.756	.860	4.067	7.445

3. Reproduction * Position

Dependent Variable: dev_azi_deg

Reproduction	Position	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
CTC	1	-5.436	1.183	-7.758	-3.114
	2	-.539	1.169	-2.834	1.756
	3	-3.332	1.212	-5.712	-.951
	4	5.514	1.228	3.103	7.925
VBAP	1	-4.270	1.169	-6.565	-1.976
	2	-5.431	1.162	-7.712	-3.149
	3	1.253	1.190	-1.084	3.589
	4	5.997	1.205	3.632	8.363

4. Reproduction * Position

Estimates

Dependent Variable: dev_azi_deg

Reproduction	Position	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
CTC	1	-5.436	1.183	-7.758	-3.114
	2	-.539	1.169	-2.834	1.756
	3	-3.332	1.212	-5.712	-.951
	4	5.514	1.228	3.103	7.925
VBAP	1	-4.270	1.169	-6.565	-1.976
	2	-5.431	1.162	-7.712	-3.149
	3	1.253	1.190	-1.084	3.589
	4	5.997	1.205	3.632	8.363

Pairwise Comparisons

Dependent Variable: dev_azi_deg

Position	(I) Reproduction	(J) Reproduction	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b
1	CTC	VBAP	-1.166	1.663	.484
	VBAP	CTC	1.166	1.663	.484
2	CTC	VBAP	4.891 [*]	1.648	.003
	VBAP	CTC	-4.891 [*]	1.648	.003
3	CTC	VBAP	-4.584 [*]	1.699	.007
	VBAP	CTC	4.584 [*]	1.699	.007
4	CTC	VBAP	-.483	1.720	.779
	VBAP	CTC	.483	1.720	.779

Pairwise Comparisons

Dependent Variable: dev_azi_deg

Position	(I) Reproduction	(J) Reproduction	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	CTC	VBAP	-4.430	2.099
	VBAP	CTC	-2.099	4.430
2	CTC	VBAP	1.655	8.127
	VBAP	CTC	-8.127	-1.655
3	CTC	VBAP	-7.919	-1.249
	VBAP	CTC	1.249	7.919
4	CTC	VBAP	-3.861	2.895
	VBAP	CTC	-2.895	3.861

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.

Univariate Tests

Dependent Variable: dev_azi_deg

Position		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Contrast	57.048	1	57.048	.491	.484
	Error	75342.408	649	116.090		
2	Contrast	1022.751	1	1022.751	8.810	.003
	Error	75342.408	649	116.090		
3	Contrast	845.510	1	845.510	7.283	.007
	Error	75342.408	649	116.090		
4	Contrast	9.157	1	9.157	.079	.779
	Error	75342.408	649	116.090		

Each F tests the simple effects of Reproduction within each level combination of the other effects shown. These tests are based on the linearly independent pairwise comparisons among the estimated marginal means.

5. Reproduction * Position

Estimates

Dependent Variable: dev_azi_deg

Reproduction	Position	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
CTC	1	-5.436	1.183	-7.758	-3.114
	2	-.539	1.169	-2.834	1.756
	3	-3.332	1.212	-5.712	-.951
	4	5.514	1.228	3.103	7.925
VBAP	1	-4.270	1.169	-6.565	-1.976
	2	-5.431	1.162	-7.712	-3.149
	3	1.253	1.190	-1.084	3.589
	4	5.997	1.205	3.632	8.363

Pairwise Comparisons

Dependent Variable: dev_azi_deg

Reproduction	(I) Position	(J) Position	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence b...
						Lower Bound
CTC	1	2	-4.897*	1.663	.020	-9.297
		3	-2.104	1.694	1.000	-6.586
		4	-10.950*	1.705	.000	-15.462
	2	1	4.897*	1.663	.020	.497
		3	2.792	1.684	.586	-1.664
		4	-6.053*	1.695	.002	-10.539
	3	1	2.104	1.694	1.000	-2.377
		2	-2.792	1.684	.586	-7.248
		4	-8.846*	1.725	.000	-13.412
	4	1	10.950*	1.705	.000	6.438
		2	6.053*	1.695	.002	1.568
		3	8.846*	1.725	.000	4.279
VBAP	1	2	1.160	1.648	1.000	-3.201
		3	-5.523*	1.668	.006	-9.936
		4	-10.268*	1.678	.000	-14.709
	2	1	-1.160	1.648	1.000	-5.521
		3	-6.683*	1.663	.000	-11.084
		4	-11.428*	1.674	.000	-15.857
	3	1	5.523*	1.668	.006	1.109
		2	6.683*	1.663	.000	2.282
		4	-4.745*	1.693	.031	-9.225
	4	1	10.268*	1.678	.000	5.826
		2	11.428*	1.674	.000	6.999
		3	4.745*	1.693	.031	.264

Pairwise Comparisons

Dependent Variable: dev_azi_deg

Reproduction	(I) Position	(J) Position	95% Confidence Interval for ... ^b
			Upper Bound
CTC	1	2	-.497
		3	2.377
		4	-6.438
	2	1	9.297
		3	7.248
		4	-1.568
	3	1	6.586
		2	1.664
		4	-4.279
	4	1	15.462
		2	10.539
		3	13.412
VBAP	1	2	5.521
		3	-1.109
		4	-5.826
	2	1	3.201
		3	-2.282
		4	-6.999
	3	1	9.936
		2	11.084
		4	-.264
	4	1	14.709
		2	15.857
		3	9.225

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.

Univariate Tests

Dependent Variable: dev_azi_deg

Reproduction		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
CTC	Contrast	5347.679	3	1782.560	15.355	.000
	Error	75342.408	649	116.090		
VBAP	Contrast	6908.316	3	2302.772	19.836	.000
	Error	75342.408	649	116.090		

Each F tests the simple effects of Position within each level combination of the other effects shown. These tests are based on the linearly independent pairwise comparisons among the estimated marginal means.

Post Hoc Tests

Position

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: dev_azi_deg

Bonferroni

(I) Position	(J) Position	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
1	2	-1.84693288	1.170427598	.690	-4.94431803
	3	-3.84939694*	1.188304579	.008	-6.99409120
	4	-10.6064797*	1.196009458	.000	-13.7715640
2	1	1.846932883	1.170427598	.690	-1.25045226
	3	-2.00246405	1.183192612	.546	-5.13363016
	4	-8.75954685*	1.190930564	.000	-11.9111904
3	1	3.84939694*	1.188304579	.008	.7047026731
	2	2.002464052	1.183192612	.546	-1.12870205
	4	-6.75708280*	1.208504290	.000	-9.95523298
4	1	10.6064797*	1.196009458	.000	7.441395510
	2	8.75954685*	1.190930564	.000	5.607903263
	3	6.75708280*	1.208504290	.000	3.558932620

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: dev_azi_deg

Bonferroni

95% Confidence ..

(I) Position	(J) Position	Upper Bound
1	2	1.250452262
	3	-.704702673
	4	-7.44139551
2	1	4.944318028
	3	1.128702050
	4	-5.60790326
3	1	6.994091197
	2	5.133630155
	4	-3.55893262
4	1	13.77156396
	2	11.91119044
	3	9.955232983

Based on observed means.

The error term is Mean Square(Error) = 116.090.

*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.

```

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  /EMMEANS=TABLES(Reproduction*Position) COMPARE(Reproduction) ADJ(BONFERRONI)
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Univariate Analysis of Variance

Notes

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Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics are based on all cases with valid data for all variables in the model.
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Notes

Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00,34
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Warnings

Post hoc tests are not performed for Reproduction because there are fewer than three groups.

Between-Subjects Factors

		N
Reproduction	CTC	338
	VBAP	342
Position	1	170
	2	169
	3	171
	4	170

Descriptive Statistics

Dependent Variable: dev_theta_deg

Reproduction	Position	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
CTC	1	-6.02697309	21.89480434	85
	2	6.380307540	15.95893498	83
	3	.3739694118	18.55858967	85
	4	1.042959871	17.79031208	85
	Total		.4074313665	19.11887667
VBAP	1	-3.33491662	13.78362633	85
	2	6.786452188	12.29821793	86
	3	9.837539535	13.65609544	86
	4	8.325705753	13.30539164	85
	Total		5.420702820	14.18447252
Total	1	-4.68094486	18.29009381	170
	2	6.586984698	14.17309547	169
	3	5.133425731	16.91005067	171
	4	4.684332812	16.08235796	170
	Total		2.928812009	16.99282914

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: dev_theta_deg

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	19858.681 ^a	7	2836.954	10.819	.000
Intercept	5809.780	1	5809.780	22.157	.000
Reproduction	4183.737	1	4183.737	15.956	.000
Position	13435.083	3	4478.361	17.079	.000
Reproduction * Position	2190.778	3	730.259	2.785	.040
Error	176206.808	672	262.213		
Total	201898.487	680			
Corrected Total	196065.488	679			

a. R Squared = .101 (Adjusted R Squared = .092)

Estimated Marginal Means

1. Reproduction

Dependent Variable: dev_theta_deg

Reproduction	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
CTC	.443	.881	-1.287	2.172
VBAP	5.404	.876	3.684	7.123

2. Position

Dependent Variable: dev_theta_deg

Position	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	-4.681	1.242	-7.120	-2.242
2	6.583	1.246	4.137	9.030
3	5.106	1.238	2.674	7.537
4	4.684	1.242	2.246	7.123

3. Reproduction * Position

Dependent Variable: dev_theta_deg

Reproduction	Position	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
CTC	1	-6.027	1.756	-9.476	-2.578
	2	6.380	1.777	2.890	9.870
	3	.374	1.756	-3.075	3.823
	4	1.043	1.756	-2.406	4.492
VBAP	1	-3.335	1.756	-6.784	.114
	2	6.786	1.746	3.358	10.215
	3	9.838	1.746	6.409	13.266
	4	8.326	1.756	4.877	11.774

4. Reproduction * Position

Estimates

Dependent Variable: dev_theta_deg

Reproduction	Position	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
CTC	1	-6.027	1.756	-9.476	-2.578
	2	6.380	1.777	2.890	9.870
	3	.374	1.756	-3.075	3.823
	4	1.043	1.756	-2.406	4.492
VBAP	1	-3.335	1.756	-6.784	.114
	2	6.786	1.746	3.358	10.215
	3	9.838	1.746	6.409	13.266
	4	8.326	1.756	4.877	11.774

Pairwise Comparisons

Dependent Variable: dev_theta_deg

Position	(I) Reproduction	(J) Reproduction	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b
1	CTC	VBAP	-2.692	2.484	.279
	VBAP	CTC	2.692	2.484	.279
2	CTC	VBAP	-.406	2.492	.871
	VBAP	CTC	.406	2.492	.871
3	CTC	VBAP	-9.464*	2.477	.000
	VBAP	CTC	9.464*	2.477	.000
4	CTC	VBAP	-7.283*	2.484	.003
	VBAP	CTC	7.283*	2.484	.003

Pairwise Comparisons

Dependent Variable: dev_theta_deg

Position	(I) Reproduction	(J) Reproduction	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	CTC	VBAP	-7.569	2.185
	VBAP	CTC	-2.185	7.569
2	CTC	VBAP	-5.298	4.486
	VBAP	CTC	-4.486	5.298
3	CTC	VBAP	-14.326	-4.601
	VBAP	CTC	4.601	14.326
4	CTC	VBAP	-12.160	-2.406
	VBAP	CTC	2.406	12.160

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.

Univariate Tests

Dependent Variable: dev_theta_deg

Position		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Contrast	308.005	1	308.005	1.175	.279
	Error	176206.808	672	262.213		
2	Contrast	6.967	1	6.967	.027	.871
	Error	176206.808	672	262.213		
3	Contrast	3828.523	1	3828.523	14.601	.000
	Error	176206.808	672	262.213		
4	Contrast	2254.131	1	2254.131	8.597	.003
	Error	176206.808	672	262.213		

Each F tests the simple effects of Reproduction within each level combination of the other effects shown. These tests are based on the linearly independent pairwise comparisons among the estimated marginal means.

5. Reproduction * Position

Estimates

Dependent Variable: dev_theta_deg

Reproduction	Position	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
CTC	1	-6.027	1.756	-9.476	-2.578
	2	6.380	1.777	2.890	9.870
	3	.374	1.756	-3.075	3.823
	4	1.043	1.756	-2.406	4.492
VBAP	1	-3.335	1.756	-6.784	.114
	2	6.786	1.746	3.358	10.215
	3	9.838	1.746	6.409	13.266
	4	8.326	1.756	4.877	11.774

Pairwise Comparisons

Dependent Variable: dev_theta_deg

Reproduction	(I) Position	(J) Position	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence b...
						Lower Bound
CTC	1	2	-12.407*	2.499	.000	-19.019
		3	-6.401	2.484	.061	-12.974
		4	-7.070*	2.484	.027	-13.643
	2	1	12.407*	2.499	.000	5.795
		3	6.006	2.499	.099	-.606
		4	5.337	2.499	.198	-1.275
	3	1	6.401	2.484	.061	-.172
		2	-6.006	2.499	.099	-12.618
		4	-.669	2.484	1.000	-7.242
	4	1	7.070*	2.484	.027	.497
		2	-5.337	2.499	.198	-11.949
		3	.669	2.484	1.000	-5.904
VBAP	1	2	-10.121*	2.477	.000	-16.675
		3	-13.172*	2.477	.000	-19.726
		4	-11.661*	2.484	.000	-18.233
	2	1	10.121*	2.477	.000	3.568
		3	-3.051	2.469	1.000	-9.585
		4	-1.539	2.477	1.000	-8.093
	3	1	13.172*	2.477	.000	6.619
		2	3.051	2.469	1.000	-3.483
		4	1.512	2.477	1.000	-5.042
	4	1	11.661*	2.484	.000	5.088
		2	1.539	2.477	1.000	-5.014
		3	-1.512	2.477	1.000	-8.065

Pairwise Comparisons

Dependent Variable: dev_theta_deg

Reproduction	(I) Position	(J) Position	95% Confidence Interval for ... ^b
			Upper Bound
CTC	1	2	-5.795
		3	.172
		4	-.497
	2	1	19.019
		3	12.618
		4	11.949
	3	1	12.974
		2	.606
		4	5.904
	4	1	13.643
		2	1.275
		3	7.242
VBAP	1	2	-3.568
		3	-6.619
		4	-5.088
	2	1	16.675
		3	3.483
		4	5.014
	3	1	19.726
		2	9.585
		4	8.065
	4	1	18.233
		2	8.093
		3	5.042

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.

Univariate Tests

Dependent Variable: dev_theta_deg

Reproduction		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
CTC	Contrast	6514.605	3	2171.535	8.282	.000
	Error	176206.808	672	262.213		
VBAP	Contrast	9071.632	3	3023.877	11.532	.000
	Error	176206.808	672	262.213		

Each F tests the simple effects of Position within each level combination of the other effects shown. These tests are based on the linearly independent pairwise comparisons among the estimated marginal means.

Post Hoc Tests

Position

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: dev_theta_deg

Bonferroni

(I) Position	(J) Position	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
1	2	-11.2679296*	1.758971250	.000	-15.9223295
	3	-9.81437059*	1.753805302	.000	-14.4551010
	4	-9.36527767*	1.756374981	.000	-14.0128076
2	1	11.2679296*	1.758971250	.000	6.613529615
	3	1.453558967	1.756405369	1.000	-3.19405142
	4	1.902651886	1.758971250	1.000	-2.75174806
3	1	9.81437059*	1.753805302	.000	5.173640223
	2	-1.45355897	1.756405369	1.000	-6.10116935
	4	.4490929189	1.753805302	1.000	-4.19163745
4	1	9.36527767*	1.756374981	.000	4.717747696
	2	-1.90265189	1.758971250	1.000	-6.55705183
	3	-.449092919	1.753805302	1.000	-5.08982328

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: dev_theta_deg

Bonferroni

95% Confidence ..

(I) Position	(J) Position	Upper Bound
1	2	-6.61352961
	3	-5.17364022
	4	-4.71774770
2	1	15.92232950
	3	6.101169350
	4	6.557051827
3	1	14.45510095
	2	3.194051417
	4	5.089823285
4	1	14.01280764
	2	2.751748055
	3	4.191637447

Based on observed means.

The error term is Mean Square(Error) = 262.213.

*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.